

Review

IoT monitoring in healthcare: A review of systems

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Abstract: One of the sectors where the Internet of Things (IoT) technology has chosen to live is healthcare. Indeed, using this revolutionary paradigm known as IoT, a variety of platforms are being built to bring patients closer to doctors. Most patients experience mobility issues across the world, and this phenomena of IoT-based health monitoring has allowed these patients to obtain healthcare without having to attend a health center. The overall goal of IoT monitoring in healthcare is to bring patients and doctors closer together. As a result, a wide range of medical sensors and other IoT components are utilized to remotely monitor medical indicators, including body temperature, body position, blood glucose level, heart rate, and blood pressure. Sensor advancements, wireless connectivity, and data processing technologies are unquestionably driving forces for data processing.

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Introduction

A report from the World Health Organization revealed that about 44% of the member states have less than one physician per thousand population [1]. The situation is more critical in developing economies. Fortunately, telemedicine has recently achieved a technological breakthrough with the emergence of the IoT. Healthcare is an important application area of IoT [2]. IoT is adopted with the general objective of enhancing service quality and reducing costs. According to Miorandi et al. [3], in order to continuously monitor patients' activities, including their medical parameters, the emerging Wearable Body Sensor Networks (WBSN) were developed. The medical devices connected to the IoT include medical sensors and wearable sensors. These sensors can be used to gather healthcare information and transmit it for onward transmission to remote medical centers. The Internet of Things with wearable biosensors has been applied to monitoring patients, tracking daily activities, and caring for the elderly. It may very well be predicted that the IoT with astute clinical sensors will improve personal satisfaction fundamentally and forestall the event of medical conditions. As a matter of fact, low-cost medical sensors can be connected with other things in the IoT wirelessly; it becomes feasible to develop implantable sensors to monitor the health conditions of patients. For example, BLE-based technologies are applied to connect things in our daily lives, such as smartphones, body sensors, home appliances, and personal computers for applications in healthcare, fitness, security, and home entertainment. On the other hand, the fact that mobile gadgets and health applications are rapidly emerging is

creating a vast market for IOT applications. Individual mobile health applications have been developed to perform healthcare tasks such as the measurement of blood pressure or recording of blood glucose [4]. [5] and [6] proposed a new concept named "Health Internet of Things (HIoT)" to exploit sensor technologies and wireless networks in monitoring medical conditions.

General overview of the remote health monitoring system

Nowadays, patients don't need to displace themselves with the aim of meeting a doctor face-to-face for consultation and prescription. This can be done remotely thanks to the advent of remote health monitoring using the internet of things and cloud computing. Indeed, wearable sensors allow a patient's health to be continuously monitored during normal daily activities [7]. For example, patients with high blood pressure, pulmonary problems, or any other chronic diseases will be monitored continuously and remotely by a physician who is located in a geographically distant area through the internet. This will overcome the problem of infrequent clinical visits that will provide a window on the physiological status of the patient [7]. The sensors connected to the patients gather information about the patient's health and transmit this information to a microcontroller-based processing board, computer, smartphone, or a custom-designed field-programmable gate array (FPGA). The sensed data is then transmitted through a cellular network like a 3G/4G, general packet radio service (GPRS), high-speed packet access (HSPA), or Long-Term Evolution (LTE) to a remote server located at the premises of the healthcare facility [8] as cited in [7]. The general overview of the remote health monitoring system is illustrated in figure 1.

Fig. 1: General overview of the remote health monitoring system (Murad et al., 2018)

Proposed systems for remote health monitoring

A plethora of proposed architectures have been developed for the purpose of remotely monitoring patients. These proposed systems differ in architecture but have a common goal, that of monitoring patients' health at a distance. Some of these systems are presented below.

Components of patient monitoring system

A non-intrusive method was proposed in [1] using the parameters included in the system to detect type-II diabetes, leading to the trend of non-intrusive healthcare monitoring. The system consists of three healthcare sensors, namely: temperature sensor, pulse sensor, and blood sensor. The user wears all the sensors to collect data. The data collected by the sensors is then transmitted to the cloud for data processing. The result will be uploaded to the connected display and BMI will be calculated by making use of the data. If the user's health status is unfavorable, the system will notify him of the disease and the preventive measures he should take. For instance, a blood sugar monitoring system could be designed as follows. We need a blood sugar monitoring probe, an Arduino micro-controller, a phone, and a computer with an internet connection. The probe detects blood sugar at regular intervals and sends the data to the phone. The data is then sent to a cloud service like Azure using a phone. Statistical reports can be generated using, most importantly, machine learning in Azure in order to predict any major health risk or warn the user when his blood-sugar levels are way up by sending a message to his phone (or his smart watch). This kind of system would be immensely helpful to diabetic patients who have a busy schedule. The benefit of this system is that health analysis can be performed at home and distance problems can be solved. It is worth noting that the system design is lightweight, wearable, and portable. The creation of this system meets the specifications of IoT, transforming the current healthcare system using IoT technology. Diabetes no longer requires a laboratory test. Detection can be done in a non-intrusive way. Figure 2 below illustrates the components of a patient monitoring system.

Fig. 2: Components of patient monitoring system (Saha et al., 2017)

The Health Care Monitoring System in Internet of Things (IoT) by Using RFID

A healthcare monitoring model that uses RFID was proposed in [9] consisting of sensors that are attached to the patient’s body, an analog to digital converter (ADC), a microcontroller, Wi-Fi network, Bluetooth wireless devices, mobile phones, Internet devices, doctors and nurses, emergency teams, hospitals, and ambulances that facilitate healthcare for the patients [10] as cited in [9]. Information to get the patient’s health details is continuously collected from the patient’s body by the sensors attached to the patient’s body. If there is any emergency, the wireless devices used for data transmission can remotely report the patient’s physical condition to the doctors. The doctor can then mobilize the emergency medical services of the hospital for necessary actions aimed at aiding the patient. Figure 3 below illustrates the different operations of healthcare monitoring using IoT and RFID. The IoT architecture of this proposed system is comprised of four layers, including a sensor layer, network layer, internet layer, and service layer. At the sensor layer, the different sensors used, such as the blood pressure sensor, EEG sensor, blood glucose sensor, temperature sensor, motion sensor, and ECG sensor, are responsible for monitoring and collecting information from the patient’s body for onward transmission to the network layer. It is worth noting that the information generated from these sensors is analog in nature and has to be converted into digital form by the Analog to Digital Converter (ADC). The information in the digital signal from the ADC is then forwarded to the RFID and Bluetooth devices via the microcontroller. The RFID or Bluetooth devices operate at the network layer of this system alongside other divergent protocols such as 2G, 3G, and 4G with routers. The internet layer is responsible for establishing the connection between the network layer and the service layer. Finally, the monitored data from the internet is directly accessible by the doctors and nurses, ambulance, emergency team, government agency, etc. According to the information received, the various teams can then harness medical resources to assist the patient remotely.

Fig. 3: Healthcare monitoring model using IoT(Khan, 2017)

Healthcare monitoring system based on IoT

A real-time monitoring system using IoT technologies is proposed in [11], where the vital parameters of patients are remotely monitored by health practitioners. The system is built using IoT hardware devices such as the Arduino board and Raspberry Pi board. The system also employs sensors such as pulse oximeters and temperature sensors. The Raspberry Pi is a small computing board weighing 50g with a power rating of 5v, 700mA. It is very cost-effective

and comes in different models: A, B, and B+ with 512 MB of RAM embedded with an ARMII processor having an operating frequency of 700 MHz [12]. The third generation of the Raspberry Pi board has additional features such as Wi-Fi Wireless N (802.11n), Bluetooth 4.1, Bluetooth Low Energy (BLE), and a microprocessor 102GHz 64-bit quad-core ARMv8 CPU. The Arduino Uno is a low-cost, simple-to-use, and programmable open-source microcontroller board that may be used in a wide range of electrical applications. This board can operate relays, LEDs, servos, and motors as an output and can be interfaced with other Arduino boards, Arduino shields, and Raspberry Pi boards. Pulse oximeters for home use are compact, lightweight, and portable monitors that take the oxygen level in the blood and the pulse rate non-invasively from the user's fingertip. A blood oxygen level of more than 95% is considered normal, whereas 92% or below indicates low blood oxygen. Adults' typical pulse rates range from 60 to 80 beats per minute, and when you exercise, your heart rate rises and your oxygen saturation drops [11]. Pulse oximetry is a valuable technique for people with Chronic Obstructive Pulmonary Disease (COPD). Monitor your oxygen saturation level at home, during exercise, and during social events. This will assist you in adjusting your oxygen flow [13]. The temperature sensor DS18B20 is used to measure the body temperature. The DS18B20 is a digital thermometer with a range of 9 to 12 bits that measures temperatures in Celsius. The DS18B20 uses a 1-Wire bus to communicate. Multiple DS18B20s can function on the same 1-Wire bus since each has a 64-bit unique address. Using a single 1-Wire bus, a single CPU can control multiple DS18B20s scattered over a large area [14].

Fig. 4: Raspberry Pi

Fig. 5: Arduino Uno

Fig. 6: Pulse Oximeter

Fig. 7: Temperature Sensor

The block diagram for a health monitoring system is shown in Figure 8 below. Body temperature, oxygen saturation, and pulse rate are all measured by the system. The system's heart is a server based on Amazon EC2, which houses the MQTT broker. The internet is accessible through the Wi-Fi router. The sensors are connected using an Arduino UNO board and a Raspberry Pi board. The temperature sensor is attached to the Arduino board, which collects the patient's body temperature and sends the information using the MQTT protocol through a Wi-Fi module [11].

Fig. 8: Healthcare monitoring system based on IoT (Krishna & Sampath, 2017)

IoT-based heart disease monitoring system

An IoT-based heart disease monitoring system for pervasive healthcare services is proposed in [16]. The system is designed to monitor a patient's physical signs such as heart rate, ECG, blood pressure, spO2, pulse rate, blood glucose, blood fat, and patient location as well as important environmental indicators continuously. As a result, the goal of this monitoring system is to give remote health practitioners access to information about their patients' health in order to detect or predict harmful situations. The sensor layer, the transport layer, and the application layer are the three layers that make up the overall architecture of IoT applications. The architecture of the IoT-based heart disease monitoring system was designed based on that general model. Data acquisition is primarily composed of sensors

carried by patients, and the selection of sensors is based on the parameter to be monitored and the sampling frequency for each parameter. Heart rate can be calculated using ECG signals. The monitoring of blood fat and glucose is not continuous since the tests for these indicators need patient interaction (picking a spot of blood from fingers and placing the test paper with blood into the sensing device) [16]. Instead, it is advised that these parameters be examined before and after a meal. The architecture of the IoT-based monitoring system for heart disease patients is shown in Figure 9 below.

Fig. 9: IoT-based heart disease monitoring system (C Li et al., 2017)

Some of the system's gadgets, as well as an example of the doctor's monitoring GUI, are depicted in the figures below. Figure 3 depicts the sensor for SpO2 and pulse rate (a). Figure 3(b) depicts the system's connector, an Android smartphone. A remote practitioner's interface for monitoring patients' SpO2 and pulse rate is also shown in Fig. 3 (c) [16]. The pulse rate sensor device takes data from the patient's finger and delivers it to an Android phone running an app that receives and saves monitored data from sensing devices via Bluetooth and provides pertinent data according to different operating modes. The physicians utilize a web program to keep an eye on the situation from a distance.

Fig. 10: (a) the SpO2 sensor device; (b) the mobile phone; (c) SpO2 monitoring data (C Li et al., 2017).

Smart Healthcare Monitoring using IoT

Banka et al. [16] proposed a system that remotely and continuously analyses numerous health indicators of patients and forecasts any sickness or problem, allowing patients to avoid the discomfort of repeated hospital visits. The suggested system may be installed in hospitals, and it can collect and store a large quantity of data in an online database. An application can also be used to obtain the findings from a mobile device. Patients may monitor their health conditions at any time from the comfort of their own homes, and only go to the hospital when absolutely necessary. This may be accomplished by employing a system whose findings are made available online and can be viewed from anywhere on the planet. The system uses different sensors such as temperature sensors, heartbeat sensors, pulse sensors, vibration sensors, blood pressure (BP) sensors, and a very cost-effective microcontroller, the Raspberry Pi, with small PC features that offer the entire Linux server and peripheral device connectivity on a single chip. This system employs the MCP3008 8-channel 10-bit analog-to-digital converter chip. The GPRS/GSM Quadband Module (SIM900) GSM module, which is designed to offer GPRS connection to the system and includes the SIM900 communication module from SIMCom, is also employed in this system. This module works with any sim card that has its own unique number. It may also be used to make phone calls or to connect to the internet by creating sockets. Because certain sensors provide analog outputs that aren't compatible with the Raspberry Pi, the analog values are transformed to digital using a convertor IC. The numerous sensors are attached to the patient's body and take readings before sending a signal to the Raspberry Pi. The Raspberry Pi is a single-board computer the size of a credit card that runs Linux. Various sensors are utilized to detect the patient's body temperature, heart rate, and blood pressure, with the findings being transmitted to a database through the Raspberry Pi and monitored.

Fig. 11: System Architecture (Banka et al., 2018)

Fig. 12: Experimental Setup (Banka et al., 2018)

Smart Healthcare Monitoring System Using Raspberry Pi on IoT Platform

Seena and Sudarshan [17] presented an IoT healthcare monitoring system based on the Raspberry Pi that would allow patients and doctors to communicate more easily. Temperature sensors, heart rate sensors, blood pressure sensors, acceleration sensors, respiration sensors, ECG sensors, and a Raspberry Pi with GSM make up the hardware unit of this system. This system's software platform makes use of languages like Python and MATLAB, as well as their interfaces. The Raspberry Pi is the central component of this system, with all other sensors attached to it. The Raspberry Pi is powered by a 5V DC source. Because not all sensors consume the same amount of electricity, transmitters are used to handle them. A step down transformer is used with V/1A values of (0-9, 15-0-15). The voltage 230V might be transformed to 0-9V and 15-0-15V, and then transmitted to a switch mode power supply (SMPS). This circuit has three integrated circuits (ICs): 7805, 7812, and 7912, which require + 5v, + 12v, and -12v volts, respectively. These diodes are then used to modify the wavelength from AC to DC. The Raspberry Pi microcontroller receives data from the sensors connected to the patient's body and generates information at every span of time and displays this information on the LCD user device and also on the doctor's device. Because it receives data from the sensors, analyzes it, saves it in its memory, and then sends it to the IoT server, the Raspberry Pi microcontroller is at the heart of this system.

Fig. 13: Architectural design with Raspberry Pi (Seena & Sudarshan, 2019)

Fig. 14: The virtual architectural model of IoT (Seena & Sudarshan, 2019)

Secured Smart Healthcare Monitoring System Based on IoT

Bhoomika and Muralidhara [18] presented an internet-based method for continuous patient monitoring. The PIC18F46K22 Microcontroller, Temperature Sensor (DS18B20), Pulse Oximeter Sensor (TCRT1000), Liquid Crystal Display (16x2), GSM MODEM, Piezo Electric Buzzer, Wi-Fi Module, Max232, GSM Modem, and Regulated Power Supply are all included in the model. This system's PIC18F46K22 microcontroller receives data from sensors and transmits it through the Wi-Fi Protocol. Doctors can view the protected data supplied at any time by typing the

corresponding unique IP address into any Internet Browser on the end-user device (ex: Laptop, Desktop, Tablet, Mobile phone). When the heart rate is greater than 90 or less than 60, the microcontroller attached to the GSM modem sends information to the doctor or caretaker. Information is sent to the doctor or caretaker when the temperature is less than 20 or greater than 35. When this is happening, the buzzer alerts the caretaker with a sound, and the LCD The transaction procedure and healthcare data are shown on the LCD, which is connected to the microcontroller. Furthermore, because the user interface html webpage will automatically refresh every 15 seconds, the doctor will be updated on the patient's health status on a regular basis. Figure 15 illustrates the suggested system architecture for IoT Healthcare.

Fig. 15: Proposed Block diagram of IOT based healthcare system (Bhoomika & Muralidhara, 2015)

Fig. 16: Designed system as with reference to block diagram (Bhoomika & Muralidhara, 2015)

Healthcare Monitoring System Using IoT

Shaikh & Chitre [19] presented an IoT healthcare monitoring system divided into two parts: hardware and software. The hardware part consists of a Raspberry Pi B+ microcontroller for data acquisition and processing, a temperature sensor, an ECG sensor, a heart rate sensor, a blood pressure sensor, and an accelerometer (ADXL 335). The software component of the system consists of a server where the data containing the detailed information of patients sent by Raspberry Pi is stored. The procedure begins once the system is turned on. The sensors connected to the body of the patient collect information related to body temperature, heart rate, weight, body position, and ECG. This information is then fed as input to the Raspberry Pi microcontroller for data processing. Data processing, in this sense, is the process of checking if the data is in a specified range. If the data is not in the specified range, it demonstrates that the patient is in a critical state and an alert is sent to the doctor. The doctor can use his login details to gain access to the patient's current and previous records, as well as make prescription and medication recommendations. Patients are also given a unique client ID and password to access their information. The patient's therapy records are saved in the cloud for easy access by both the patient and the physician (doctor).

Fig. 17: Block diagram of the healthcare monitoring system using IoT (Shaikh & Chitre, 2017)

Fig. 18: System Architecture (Shaikh & Chitre, 2017)

Conclusions

The possibility for objects to connect to the internet allows people to, on the one hand, monitor the status and environment around them, and on the other hand, operate these things remotely from anywhere in the globe [20]. Since Kevin Ashton's conception of the Internet of Things in 1999, it has matured and stretched its tentacles across practically every aspect of human life [21]. In the field of healthcare, the internet of things is crucial. Because of this paradigm change, many patients all around the world now have access to some of the most accomplished doctors of our day. This article's goal was to show how the internet of things may be used in healthcare for remote monitoring. As a result, this article described a number of technologies created for remote healthcare monitoring. The following systems were presented after a broad description of the remote health monitoring system was given: Components of a patient monitoring system; RFID-based Internet of Things (IoT) Healthcare Monitoring System; IoT-based heart disease monitoring system; Smart Healthcare Monitoring using IoT; IoT Platform-Based Smart Healthcare Monitoring System Using Raspberry Pi; Secured Smart Healthcare Monitoring System Based on IoT; Healthcare Monitoring System Using IoT. The above-mentioned healthcare remote monitoring systems are made up of hardware and software components and operate on a four-layered IoT architecture, which includes the sensor layer, network layer, internet layer, and service layer. Sensors connected to the patient's body capture information about his or her health and send it to a microcontroller for processing. The data from the microcontroller is then sent across a wireless network to a server on the internet, where it can be seen by both the patient and the doctor. With this data on the cloud, the doctor can keep an eye on the patient at all times.

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